

Objectives

- 1) Efficient capacitation of BUU academic and R&I staff on consumer behavior analysis, innovative business modelling methodologies and related digital tools;
- 2) Efficient capacitation of BUU on research management and administration;
- 3) Creation of the BUU BMI Laboratory

- **TITLE**
Listening The Consumer
- **RESPONSIBLE PARTNER**
ULE
- **CONTENT**
The workshops will be focused to consumer relations.
- **FORMAT**
Online
- **SCHEDULE**
4 workshops of 3 days duration

Capacitation in Consumer Behaviour Analysis

- **TITLE**
Innovation and Sustainability Workshop
- **RESPONSIBLE PARTNER**
ULE
- **CONTENT**
The workshops will be focused to Innovation and Entrepreneurship and Sustainable and Knowledge Management
- **FORMAT**
Online
- **SCHEDULE**
6 workshops of 1 day duration

Capacitation in Innovative Business Models, Entrepreneurship Strategies, Methodologies and Tools

- **TITLE**
Master of Science Strategy, Enterprise & Innovation
- **RESPONSIBLE PARTNER**
ATU
- **CONTENT**
Based the ATU official Masters' Degree, the programme incorporates workshop modules that focus on the practical capabilities required by BUU to increase their scientific excellence, which will in turn enable to help Turkish companies to improve business performance and competitiveness leading to economic development in the region
- **FORMAT**
Online and face to face
- **SCHEDULE**
27 lecture days

- **TITLE**
BMI Laboratory Set-Up
- **RESPONSIBLE PARTNER**
ATU & ULE
- **CONTENT**
Helping BUU to establish BMI Laboratory
- **FORMAT**
Face to face
- **SCHEDULE**
2 workshops

Capacitation in BMI Laboratory Set-Up

- **TITLE**
Academic and Scientific Writing
- **RESPONSIBLE PARTNER**
ULE
- **CONTENT**
Provide a comprehensive set of abilities and resources to prepare high-impact scientific communications
- **FORMAT**
Online
- **SCHEDULE**
6 workshops of 1 day duration

Capacitation in Innovative Academic Writing